

An analysis of factors affecting student wellbeing: Emotional intelligence, family and school environment

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to identify the role of family and school environments in predicting emotional intelligence and student well-being. It also examines whether or not emotional intelligence acts as a mediator. A total of 500 senior high school students from 16 private high schools in Pemalang District, Indonesia, completed this survey in the 2020-2021 academic year. Data analysis was carried out using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis with Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS). The results show that family environment affects the fulfilment of student well-being. Emotional intelligence was not an essential mediator in the relationship between the family environment and student well-being. The school environment also had a decisive role in fulfilling student well-being. Emotional intelligence was an essential mediator between the school environment and student well-being. Student well-being should be realized. It is necessary to address the welfare of teachers in the school environment and the awareness of parents in the family to assist students. Teachers' and students' interests are closely related. When the welfare of teachers is prioritized, it will improve harmonious relationships in the school environment. Likewise, when parents accompany their children at home, the children will feel more prosperous.

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1. INTRODUCTION

School is an institution from which students obtain formal education. The excellent experience the school gives will make students feel prosperous (student well-being). Well-being is the primary function of education in Indonesia, as adopted from a public school in England quoted in Morris's article, that teaches 'happiness' through a cyclical process of self-management characterized as 'awareness', 'intervention', and 'action', delivered through a curriculum that includes: caring for the body; philosophy and wellbeing; emotions; resilience; strength and flow; relationships [1]. Therefore, all schools need to develop student well-being in the learning process. Creating a pleasant learning environment makes students feel happy to take part in learning activities, including intracurricular, curricular, and extracurricular activities, which can be assumed to realize student well-being. Some important factors influencing children's well-being are family, friends, health, appearance, free time, future, home, money, ownership, school, and choices in life [2].

Student well-being is currently a primary concern for school teachers [3]. Therefore, schools have an important role in realizing student well-being. Participation in activities at school can also be linked to psychosocial well-being [4]. Thus, student well-being improvement program must be implemented in the school environment. When students have high well-being, they feel happy and prosperous, and will be able to follow the learning process in the classroom [5].

An educator has several essential points in fulfilling student well-being in the school environment. One of the issues related to educators are that teachers have a crucial role and duty for human life [6]. Then, teachers are the second parents of students. Furthermore, the teachers create a conducive, fun school environment. The last is that teachers have a role in presenting a fun class. Teachers will lead their students to become valuable human beings with these responsibilities. However, education in Indonesia is facing the high number of violence cases. Based on the Indonesian Child Protection Commission (ICPC or KPAI) data, from January to October 2019, 127 cases were experienced by students, including physical, psychological, and sexual violence [7]. The violence involves teachers or principals, students, and parents of students. This case is contrary to student well-being; when schools do not pay attention to violence, students will feel uncomfortable in learning.

Schools are not the only institution responsible for fulfilling students' well-being; families also have an equally important role. Paying attention to individual development and the need to develop the family's intelligence are essential. Support from the family significantly affects children's well-being, affecting their academic achievements [8]. Every child has a different potential for intelligence or multiple intelligence. However, many parents only consider the academic achievements of children without paying attention to other aspects of intelligence. A survey by the Indonesian Child Protection Commission (ICPC or KPAI) shows that 66.4% of fathers and 71% of mothers of 800 family respondents educated their children by imitating the education of their parents who prioritized academic development [9]. Various problems in the family environment, such as violence, make it difficult for children to develop their potential and hinder student well-being. To develop a child's interests, talents, and intelligence optimally, strong family support is needed. On the other hand, multiple intelligences can improve the quality of student learning in doing independent tasks. For example, multiple intelligence-based learning education has been proven to have an impact on students' social science performance [10]. Students prefer to study based on their talents and choose a learning style [11].

Based on previous research, curricular activities and parents' role influence student well-being, and the feeling in the school community can improve student well-being [12]. Making material changes in addition to organizational and cultural developments is essential. Significant and sound changes, such as studying outside the classroom, can support learning opportunities that create student well-being [13]. Teachers' perceptions of student needs, satisfaction and well-being are unrelated to emotional difficulties and student behavior. The relationship between teachers and students is strongly predicted [14]. Several studies revealed factors that can affect student well-being and quality of life in adolescence; student well-being combines affective, behavioral, and cognitive dimensions [15], [16]. Some literature shows a relationship between emotional intelligence and well-being [17].

People who can express, understand, and regulate feelings psychologically and socially have a high level of well-being [18]. What factors support students' emotional intelligence in realizing their well-being? Whether or not the family environment and the school environment have an essential role in influencing emotional intelligence and student well-being is discussed in this study. This study aims to determine whether or not the school environment and family environment affect student well-being. Contribution of the research is related to the role of emotional intelligence concerning student well-being. Emotional intelligence is considered as mediating the family environment and school environment, and student well-being. The first objective is to explain the role of the family environment and school environment in predicting emotional intelligence and student well-being; to examine whether or not emotional intelligence acts as a mediator in the relationship between the family environment, school environment, and student well-being.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

A total of 500 students completed this survey in the 2020-2021 academic year. Students in this sample were from 16 private high schools in Pemalang District, Indonesia. The students were between 15 and 19 years old. The sample consisted of 95 (19%) male students and 405 (81%) female students. Most of the father's education was elementary school (n=254, 50.8%), and the mother's education was elementary school (n=272, 54.4%). In addition, 24.2% (n=121) of fathers and 15.8% (79) of mothers had high school education. A total of 16.4% (n=82) fathers and 22.2% (n=111) mothers graduated from junior high school; 4.6% (n=23) fathers and 4% (n=20) mothers did not attend school. Then, 4% (n=20) of fathers and 3.6% (n=18) of mothers had Bachelor Degree (S1)/ Magister (S2)/ Doctoral (S3).

The condition of the family environment was measured by indicators of the family environment in the success of children's education, which consists of how parents educate children, relationships between family members, home atmosphere, family economic conditions, understanding of parents, and cultural background [19]. Validity and reliability tests used construct reliability and validity with Cronbach alpha value criteria >0.7 [20]; $\rho_A > 0.7$; Composite Reliability (CR) > 0.6 [20]; Average Variance Extracted (AVE) > 0.5 [20]. The results of construct reliability and validity in family environment variables show Cronbach alpha = 0.797, $\rho_A = 0.802$; CR = 0.849; and the AVE value = 0.417. Based on these results, the family environment variable had a reliable value, indicated by the original sample value > 0.7 , namely 0.849. Meanwhile, the AVE value has a value below 0.5 (0.417). However, the value of composite reliability was greater than 0.6. In addition, the ρ_A value can be used to determine the variable that meets convergent validity provided that the ρ_A value is greater than 0.7 [20]. It can be seen that the ρ_A value is 0.802 so that the family environment variable can be accepted and meets convergent validity.

The condition of the school environment was seen in the intra-curricular [21], [22], extracurricular activities [23]–[25], and the school culture [26]. The school environment was measured by using a closed questionnaire. The results of construct reliability and validity in the school environment show Cronbach alpha = 0.753, $\rho_A = 0.759$; CR = 0.822, and the AVE value = 0.368. Based on these results, the school environment variable has a reliable value, indicated by the original sample value > 0.7 , 0.822. Thus, the ρ_A value is 0.822, so that the school environment variable can be accepted and meets convergent validity.

According to Reuven Bar on [27], emotional intelligence can be seen from: intrapersonal, interpersonal skills, adaptability, stress management strategies, motivation, and mood. Emotional intelligence is measured using a closed questionnaire. The results of construct reliability and validity on emotional intelligence show Cronbach alpha = 0.857, $\rho_A = 0.863$; CR = 0.886, and the AVE value = 0.441. Based on these results, the emotional intelligence variable has a reliable value, indicated by the original sample value > 0.7 , 0.886. It can be seen that the ρ_A value is 0.863. So, the emotional intelligence variable can be accepted and meets convergent validity.

Student well-being was measured based on indicators that refer to the dimensions expressed by Fraillon [28], which are intrapersonal dimension and the interpersonal dimension. The intrapersonal dimensions were emotional regulation: resilience, self-esteem, curiosity, involvement, mastery of orientation, and interpersonal dimension: communicative effectiveness, empathy, acceptance, and connection. The results of construct reliability and validity on emotional intelligence show Cronbach alpha = 0.835, $\rho_A = 0.841$; CR = 0.869, and the AVE value = 0.358. Based on these results, the student well-being variable has a reliable value, indicated by the original sample value > 0.7 , namely, 0.869. It can be seen that the ρ_A value is 0.841. So, the student well-being variable can be accepted and meets convergent validity.

Data analysis was carried out using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method with the Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) type. The data were processed by using Smart PLS 3 software. In Table 1, descriptive statistics are presented, with data on the family environment, school environment, emotional intelligence, and student well-being.

Table 1. Mean and standard deviation (SD) of the independent and dependent variables

	Variable	Mean	SD
Family environment	Relation	2.818	0.99
	Comfortable	6.382	1.413
	Economic	3.296	0.945
	Motivation	6.598	1.342
	Family's habits	7.302	0.977
School environment	Intra-curricular	5.836	1.352
	Extracurricular	6.21	1.137
	School culture	12.532	1.678
Emotional intelligence	Intrapersonal	6.176	1.049
	Interpersonal	6.226	1.056
	Adaptability	5.886	1.038
	Stress management	5.992	0.988
	Mood motivation	6.15	1.045
Student well-being	Controlling emotion	3.118	0.651
	Resilient in facing problems	2.86	0.783
	Having high self-esteem	6.026	1.046
	Having a high curiosity	2.846	0.7
	Participating in school activities	6.004	1.145
	Persevere in the learning process	2.96	0.689
	Communicating	2.918	0.704
	Positioning themselves	6.51	0.999
	Confident interacting	2.914	0.659
	Good relationships	3.316	0.645

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 presents the structural figure of the Smart PLS model, where the value R^2 lies in the endogenous variable blue circle emotional intelligence and student well-being. The R^2 value of emotional intelligence of 0.321 means that the family and school environments explain 32.1% of the variance in emotional intelligence. The two exogenous variables have a construct toward emotional intelligence. Meanwhile, the R^2 student well-being is 0.586, meaning that 58.6% of the variance in student well-being can be explained by family environment, school environment, and emotional intelligence. These three variables have constructs that lead to student well-being. Chin [29] described the strength R^2 as 0.19 was weak, 0.33 was moderate, and 0.67 was substantial. Therefore, the R^2 emotional intelligence model was moderate, and the student well-being model was significant.

Table 2 shows the magnitude of the influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables. Smart PLS automatically indicates the output f^2 . According to Cohen [30], the value of $f^2 = 0.02$ suggests that the magnitude of the influence was classified as weak, 0.15 was classified as moderate, and 0.35 was classified as strong/significant.

Figure 1. Structural model smart PLS results

Table 2. SEM-PLS: f^2

Construct	f^2	Information
Family environment → emotional intelligence	0.007	Weak
Family environment → student well-being	0.027	Weak
School environment → emotional intelligence	0.355	Strong
School environment → student well-being	0.272	Moderate
Emotional intelligence → student well-being	0.242	Moderate

Source: Output Smart PLS, f^2

Table 2 shows that two weak substantive influences: emotional intelligence → student well-being. In addition, two substantive effects are moderate in value: school environment → student well-being and emotional intelligence → student well-being. Meanwhile, a strong influence was the school environment's → emotional intelligence. In testing which hypothesis was accepted, the bootstrap output was used by looking at the path coefficients table. The significance of weights can be seen in both t-values and p-values. For

example, at the 5% significance level, if the t -value > 1.96 or the p -value < 0.05 , it can be assumed that the path coefficient was significant [31].

Based on the correlation between research variables, the family environment had no significant effect on emotional intelligence. However, the family environment was positively and significantly correlated with student well-being. The school environment had a positive and significant impact on emotional intelligence and had a significant and positive effect on student well-being. Emotional intelligence had a positive and significant effect on student well-being. Similar to the direct effect, Smart PLS also measured the indirect effect coefficient in the construct. Both constructs used emotional intelligence as the mediating variable. The path coefficients indirect effect of Table 3 shows that emotional intelligence does not mediate or affect the relationship between family environment- emotional intelligence - student well-being (T -value $1.687 < 1.96$ and P -value $0.092 > 0.05$). Meanwhile, emotional intelligence acted as full mediation or indirect only in the school environment's \rightarrow emotional intelligence \rightarrow student well-being (T -value $8.375 > 1.96$ and P -value $0.000 < 0.05$).

Table 3. PLS-SEM: Inner model

Hypothesis		Original sample	T-value	P-value	Information	Decision	Relationship
H1	Family environment \rightarrow Emotional intelligence	0.074	1.725	0.085	Not significant	Hypothesis null rejected	
H2	Family environment \rightarrow Student well-being	0.116	3.594	0.000	Significant	Hypothesis null accepted	
H3	School environment \rightarrow Emotional intelligence	0.533	13.282	0.000	Significant	Hypothesis null accepted	
H4	School environment \rightarrow Student well-being	0.424	11.288	0.000	Significant	Hypothesis null accepted	
H5	Emotional intelligence \rightarrow Student well-being	0.384	10.982	0.000	Significant	Hypothesis null accepted	
H6	Family environment \rightarrow Emotional intelligence \rightarrow Student well-being	0.028	1.687	0.092	Not significant	Hypothesis null accepted	No mediation, no effect
H7	School environment \rightarrow Emotional intelligence \rightarrow Student well-being	0.205	8.375	0.000	Significant	Hypothesis null rejected	Complete mediation, indirect only

Source: Output Smart PLS, Path coefficients

This study broadens the understanding of the support of the family and school environments. It looks at how emotional intelligence was related to fulfilling student well-being. Satisfaction of student well-being is essential and needs attention from various parties. In the United Kingdom and Israel, meeting the needs and desires of students and concern for the well-being, teaching and learning of students by academics are encouraged by the government [32]. The higher the orientation of students' well-being values, the higher their motivation for not doing things that are not desired [33]. This study found that the family environment affects the fulfilment of student well-being. The results also show that emotional intelligence is not an essential mediator between family environment and student well-being. Apart from the family environment, the school environment also had a decisive role in fulfilling student well-being. The findings also show that emotional intelligence is essential to the school environment and student well-being.

This study emphasizes the results of previous research showing the importance of family and school support in fulfilling student well-being. Spirituality and religious factors in everyday life are essential to improve student well-being [34]. Indeed, there is no difference in psychological well-being and academic achievement regarding family structure and living arrangements, but there is a difference in well-being in the condition of the family's social environment (whole family or living with a nuclear family) [35], [36]. Living away from parents temporarily negatively affects the well-being of high school students. Therefore, students who live with their parents are assumed to have increased well-being than those who do not live with their parents. Parents play a role in creating fun learning at home that will affect the success of children's education. This is proven during the COVID-19 pandemic where students study more at home [37].

Several studies indicate that school conditions affect student well-being. Student well-being and performance determinants are educators, counsellors, academic advisors, and professionals [38]. The school community can improve student well-being [12], especially peer relationships [39]. Well-being is related to feelings and attitudes; family and friend relationships are the key factors. Children categorized as having high well-being tend to refer to family relationships, while those classified as having lower well-being tend to refer to relationships with friends [15]. Other studies have shown that teachers' perceptions of needs

satisfaction and well-being are unrelated to emotional difficulties and student behavior. Instead, the relationship between teachers and students strongly predicts this difficulty [14]. A teacher needs to ensure children's right in educational practice [40].

There is a relationship between school environment and student well-being [41], [42]. Parents play a significant role in school choice. It means that school conditions affect the well-being of students. Apart from these factors, the curriculum structure and rating scale are modifiable learning environment factors affecting student well-being [43]. Therefore, making material changes and organizational and cultural developments are imperative. Significant and sound changes, such as studying outside the classroom, can support learning opportunities that create student well-being [13].

Second, this study considered emotional intelligence as a variable that affects student well-being. This study showed that emotional intelligence mediates the relationship between the school environment and student well-being, but it does not mediate the relationship between family and student well-being. In contrast, emotional intelligence varies widely concerning family income, the profession of mothers and fathers, education levels of mothers and fathers, and pre-school experience [44]. Parent-child relationships and family environment influence the development of emotional regulation, a key component of emotional intelligence [45]. There is a direct correlation between the family environment and emotional intelligence; there is no difference between men and women [46].

Emotional intelligence combines the complexities of individual abilities concerning their emotional and social health. Emotional development largely depends on the quality of the family environment [47]. Youths differ in emotional intelligence based on gender, study program, and family income. It is better if emotional intelligence among adolescents can be fostered by providing an appropriate family environment and educational institutions. A bad family environment drives children to become a victim of cyberbullying, affecting student well-being and emotional intelligence [48].

The quality of parent-child relationships is often associated with children's behavior. Parental style significantly influences children's development [49]. Parental autonomy impacts valuable values to motivate students in determining future careers [50]. In addition to family environmental problems, children's experiences at an early age also affect emotional intelligence [51]. Children's moral education instilled by parents since childhood has a good influence on children's morals when they are teenagers [52]. Apart from instilling moral education, parents also influence children's media literacy education [53]. For example, parental supervision is needed, so that children are not addicted to smartphones. The level of smartphone addiction can affect students' quality of life [54]. The story of parental involvement with activities carried out at school also helps improve children's emotional well-being to build children's success in understanding the world during adolescence, which is related to emotional health and well-being. For example, bullying experienced by students makes the school atmosphere uncomfortable. It turns out that this depends on the family environment. A bad family environment can increase the likelihood of students being victims or perpetrators of cyberbullying, while a good family environment will reduce this possibility [50].

Emotional intelligence is crucial for students because it leads to academic activities [55]. Higher emotional intelligence will increase well-being and better academic quality [56]. With emotional intelligence, a child will find it easier to adapt to his social environment. Emotional intelligence is a protective factor from depression, anxiety, and stress or mental health. If this effort is made in schools, emotional intelligence can improve student well-being [18], [57]. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the psychological conditions in the environment that contribute to the emotional development of students [58]. Students' interpersonal skills affect their academic achievement. Achievement in literary studies is widely supported by those with interpersonal skills compared to those who lack interpersonal skills [56]. Training related to emotional intelligence can overcome disruptive behavior problems by focusing on school climate, classroom management, and a culture of discipline created in school rules among students [55]. The psychological component also needs to be included in the school curriculum because it is helpful for socio-emotional and academic purposes [16]. There needs to be cooperation between counselling teachers, academic supervisors and parents in increasing students' academic optimism [59].

The dysfunctional family dynamics caused by inappropriate rules and ties result in insufficient and unsatisfactory relationships in the future [60]. The level of an individuals' emotional skills depends on a person's genes, family environment, socialization, personal experience and education [61]. Although most of the literature suggests that family environment influences emotional intelligence, the level of education as an essential determinant underpinning this effect has received little empirical attention. The family environment fosters emotional intelligence in early adolescence. Early adolescents with fewer family members have higher emotional intelligence [62]. Furthermore, the father's education moderates the relationship between the family environment and emotional intelligence. Specifically, early adolescents tend to show higher levels of emotional intelligence at higher levels of the family environment when fathers have higher levels of education.

Therefore, it is necessary to continue to focus on the role of parental education when assessing the relationship between the family environment and the emotional intelligence of early adolescents [63]. The family environment and childhood trauma components are not significantly related to abilities or emotional intelligence traits [64]. Fathers' perceptions of conflict were negatively related to flexibility, reality testing, stress management, impulse control, acceptance and care about independence, reality testing, general mood, and optimism. It is interesting to note that cohesive mothers at home influence adolescents who are high in interpersonal relationships, empathetic, adaptable, have increased problem-solving skills, have high-stress management skills, and are very emotionally intelligent [65].

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the correlation between research variables, it appears that, first, family environment does not significantly affect emotional intelligence. Then the second, the family environment positively and significantly correlates with student well-being. After that, the school environment positively and significantly impacts emotional intelligence. Therefore, the school environment significantly and positively affects student well-being. Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on student well-being. The correlation between research variables indicates that, first, family environment does not significantly affect emotional intelligence. Then, the family environment positively and significantly correlates with student well-being. The school environment positively and significantly impacts emotional intelligence. Therefore, the school environment significantly and positively affects student well-being. Finally, emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on student well-being.

Based on the findings of this study, it could be suggested that there is a need for a link between the family environment and the school environment to become an essential role in fulfilling student well-being, at least for students in this study. Although emotional intelligence plays a critical role in predicting student well-being, emotional intelligence cannot be expected from the family environment. On the other hand, the school environment was a critical predictor of its effect on emotional intelligence and student well-being. Therefore, further research was needed to analyze why the family environment cannot predict students' emotional intelligence. There is a need for a link between the family environment and the school environment to achieve student well-being, at least for students in this study. Although emotional intelligence plays a critical role in predicting student well-being, emotional intelligence cannot be expected from the family environment.

On the other hand, the school environment was a critical predictor of its effect on emotional intelligence and student well-being. Therefore, further research is needed to analyze why family environment cannot predict students' emotional intelligence. This study offers new knowledge about the vital contribution of emotional intelligence to student well-being. Thus, education should focus on academic intelligence and the development of emotional intelligence.

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